

SELF-PACED LEARNING

By Using Edlink

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SEVIMA
EdLink

LEARNING PLATFORM

THE REASONS

01

WORKS

OF OUR NATION

02

FREE &

LOT OF FEATURES

03

SUPPORTED

IOS & ANDROID

SELF-PACED LEARNING

Learners can learn independently by accessing information or course material online via the internet (Online).

THE WEB DISPLAY & THE SMARTPHONE APPLICATION DISPLAY

MODUL 1

LEARNING OUTCOME

WHAT IS RHYME?

01
A rhyme is a repetition of similar sounding words, occurring at the end of lines in poems or songs. A rhyme is a tool utilizing repeating patterns that bring rhythm or musicality to poems.

02
Rhyme is a popular literary device in which the repetition of the same or similar sounds occurs in two or more words, usually at the end of lines in poems or songs.

TYPES OF RHYMES

Perfect
Only people recognize "perfect rhymes" as the only real type of rhyme. For example, "hand" and "band" are perfect rhymes, whereas "mad" and "bad" are an imperfect match in sounds.

Eye
Rhyme on words that look the same but which are actually pronounced differently – for example "tough" and "rough".

Slant
This rhyme also called as an imperfect rhyme, near rhyme, oblique, etc. This rhyme is a type of rhyme with words that have similar, but not identical sounds like "worm" and "swarm".

Rich
Rhyme using two different words that happen to sound the same (i.e. homonyms) – for example "raise" and "raze".

MODUL 2 RHYME

Detail Materi

- The basic definition of rhyme is two words that sound alike.
- Usually, the vowel sounds are the same and the consonant is different.
 - Book, nook

The Definition of Rhyme

Sesi ke 2
Basic English Literature

Type "understand" below to get the certificate at the end of the activity.

Lampiran

Definition and Types.pptx Unduh

Suka Komentari

Edlink

What is rhyme?

- The basic definition of rhyme is two words that sound alike.
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Dokumen

Definition and Types.pptx Unduh

Basic English Literature
This is the literature for A-Class

Pengelola
Achmad Nur Ravi

Pin
STON6

Sesi Pembelajaran

- Sesi ke 1 Modul 1 1 Materi
- Sesi ke 2 Modul 2 1 Materi
- Sesi ke 3 Modul 3 1 Materi
- Sesi ke 4 Modul 4 1 Materi

MODUL 3

EXAMPLES OF RHYME

- ABAB
- ABCB
- AABBA
- AABB

RHYME SCHEME IN POETRY

There are endless numbers of rhyme schemes that may manifest in a poem, but some of the most popular ones include

MODUL 4

THE SCHEME OF RHYME

The screenshot shows the Edlink mobile application interface. On the left, there is a sidebar menu with 'Sesi Pembelajaran' (Learning Sessions) including Modul 2, Modul 3, Modul 4, Modul 5, and Quiz. The main content area displays the lesson 'The Scheme of Rhyme' with the following text and rhyme scheme:

I do not like green eggs and ham. A
 I do not like them Sam I am. A
 I do not like them in a boat. B
 I do not like them with a goat. B
 I do not like them in a house. C
 I do not like them with a mouse. C

Below the text, there is a 'Dokumen' (Documents) section with a file named 'Scheme of Rhyme.pptx' and an 'Unduh' (Download) button. On the right side of the screen, there is a 'Basic English Literature' section with a 'Keluar Grup' (Leave Group) button and a 'Pin' section with the code 'STON6'.

The screenshot shows the 'Detail Materi' (Material Detail) page in the Edlink mobile application. The page title is 'Detail Materi'. The main content area displays the lesson 'The Scheme of Rhyme' with the following text and rhyme scheme:

I do not like green eggs and ham. A
 I do not like them Sam I am. A
 I do not like them in a boat. B
 I do not like them with a goat. B
 I do not like them in a house. C
 I do not like them with a mouse. C

Below the text, there is a 'The Scheme of Rhyme' section with a 'Sesi ke 4' (Session 4) and 'Basic English Literature' label. The text reads: 'Type "understand" below to get the certificate at the end of the activity.' Below this, there is a 'Lampiran' (Attachment) section with a file named 'Scheme of Rhyme.pptx' and an 'Unduh' (Download) button. At the bottom of the screen, there are 'Suka' (Like) and 'Komentari' (Comment) buttons.

MODUL 5 ASSIGNMENT

MODUL 6 QUIZ

The screenshot shows a web browser interface for Edlink. The main content area displays a quiz titled "Quiz About Rhyme" with 10 questions. The results section shows a score of 80, 10 questions, 16 minutes and 33 seconds duration, 8 correct answers, and 2 incorrect answers. A table lists the first three questions:

No	Soal	Skor	Benar	Salah
#1	What Is Rhyme?	10	1	0
#2	What is Rhyme Scheme?	10	1	0
#3	Night-Flight-Tight-...What is ...	10	1	0

The mobile app interface shows the "Detail Kuis" screen for "Basic English Literature". It displays a score of 80 (Great!) and a rank of #1. A button labeled "Lihat Laporan Kuis" is visible at the bottom.

This is a partial screenshot of a mobile app interface showing a list of questions. The visible text includes:

- mu adalah A
- Correct
- Wrong
- ftar semua pertanyaan
- rhyme?
- mu adalah A
- rhyme Scheme?
- mu adalah B
- ght-Tight-...
- mu adalah A
- a word that have simi...
- mu adalah A
- 5. Pattern of rhyme, Formation of...
- Jawaban kamu adalah B

CERTIFICATE

CERTIFICATE OF EXCELLENCE

THIS CERTIFIES THAT

NURA

successfully completed Self-Paced Study
About The Basic of Literature "Rhyme".
On 14th January 2021

SEVIMA
EdLink

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THANKS A LOT!

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